

The Unjournal

Evaluation 1 of "Accelerating Vaccine Innovation for Emerging Infectious Diseases via Parallel Discovery"

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Summary Measures

We asked evaluators to give some overall assessments, in addition to ratings across a range of criteria. *See the evaluation summary “metrics” [link evaluation summary here] for a more detailed breakdown of this. See these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis in our [data presentation here](#).*

	Rating	90% Credible Interval
Overall assessment	55/100	45 - 63
Journal rank tier, normative rating	3.5/5	2.6 - 4.8

Overall assessment: We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): “On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#))” *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best”.*

See [here](#) for the full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.